

Vertical Load Given to the Elastic Rods Intensifier

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Abstract: In this article, the process of elastic rods of the potato digger with the soil blade, developed taking into account the soil and climate conditions of our country, is presented. Also, the load value of the elastic rods of intensifier affecting the soil in the process of digging potatoes was determined.

Keywords: vertical loading, intensifier, rods, toothed sprocket, energy-saving, parameter.

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Harvesting potatoes is one of the most labor-intensive processes in potato cultivation. Currently, 75 percent of all costs in potato cultivation are related to the harvesting process. The soil and climatic conditions of our republic (high summer temperatures, low relative humidity, soil compaction as a result of irrigation) have not led to their widespread use. Because the test results of potato harvesting machines show that during the harvesting process, the soil in the potato layer is not well crushed and the soil is separated into large pieces, which reduces the degree of sieving in elevators and screens, and makes it difficult to separate the potatoes from the soil [1].

In order to crush the hard pieces on the surface of the potato tubers, which negatively affect the performance of the potato digger, a special support-crushing device is installed on the potato digger at the beginning of the technological process, then the distance between the coulters is adjusted, the required part of the potato tubers is dug out, a small amount of soil is transferred to the sieves, and they are sieved. It is necessary to reduce the number of sieves to increase the level and reduce potato loss and damage. Accordingly, we propose a potato digger design with vibrating intensifiers installed on the sieve in order to ensure the degree of soil sieving in accordance with agrotechnical requirements by reducing the metal volume of the potato digger without increasing the number of sieves. The intensifier with a toothed star consists of two toothed stars and an arrow connecting them at their centers, as well as elastic springs woven around their perimeters. The vertical load exerted by the tines of the potato digger, improved with the proposed intensifier with a toothed star, on the soil surface allows us to extract potatoes from the soil without damaging them.

Taking into account the above, we determine the vertical load applied to the spiked intensifier in the condition that it ensures the soil compaction at the required level. For this purpose, the intensifier with a fan should work at a certain depth. Taking into account these points, we determine the vertical load applied to the noise intensifier using the scheme shown in Fig. 1. According to it, we can express the total vertical load Q_y given to the fan intensifier as follows [2]

$$Q_{yu} = 2(Q_y + Q_{pa}), \quad (1)$$

where Q_y , Q_{pa} are the vertical load applied to the upper and lower beams, respectively, N.

Figure 1. Diagram for determining the vertical load applied to the shaft of a helical intensifier

According to this diagram (Figure 1) and the results of previous theoretical studies, it was found that two forces act simultaneously on the soil mass above the elevator. Therefore, if we assume that the top part of the intensifier with a suction cup on the ground above the elevator sinks into a hole equal to its diameter, or h , and the vertical load applied to it is Q_y , then the bottom part sinks into a hole equal to h and the load applied to it is kPa . To determine Q_y , we determine the elemental surface area of the uppermost layer of liquid interacting with the soil using the following expression [2, 3, 4]

$$dS = L_{st} \frac{d_{ch}}{2} d\alpha ,$$

where L_{st} is the length of the part of the liquid immersed in the soil layer located on the elevator, m; $d\alpha$ is the elemental angle (Fig. 2).

The following elemental normal forces act on the surface of the elemental surface:

$$dN = \sigma dS = \sigma L_{st} \frac{d_{ch}}{2} d\alpha, \quad (2)$$

where σ is the relative resistance of the soil to compression by the viscous intensifier fluid, Pa.

Figure 2. Scheme for determining Q_y

The sum of the normal forces and the vertical forces of the elements affecting the stiffness of the intensifier is equal to Q_y [2], i.e.:

$$Q_y = \sum dN_z = \int_{-\left(\frac{\pi + \varphi_1}{4} + \frac{\varphi_1}{2}\right)}^{\left(\frac{\pi + \varphi_1}{4} + \frac{\varphi_1}{2}\right)} dN \cos \alpha = \int_{-\left(\frac{\pi + \varphi_1}{4} + \frac{\varphi_1}{2}\right)}^{\left(\frac{\pi + \varphi_1}{4} + \frac{\varphi_1}{2}\right)} \sigma L_{st} \frac{d_{ch}}{2} \cos \alpha d\alpha, \quad (3)$$

where $dN_z - dN$ vertical formation of elementary normal force, N.

We express σ in expression (2) in terms of the magnitude of the deformation of the soil at the point of blackening and its volumetric compression coefficient [2, 4, 5]

$$\sigma = q_0 \left(1 + k_v V_e^2\right) \left[h_{yu} - \frac{d_{ch}}{2} (1 - \cos \alpha) \right] \quad (4)$$

where q_0 is the volume compression coefficient of the soil, N/m³;

Coefficient of proportionality taking into account k_v -speed, s²/m²;

Velocity of the elevator, m/s.

Taking (4) into account, we reduce (3) to the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q_y &= \int_{-\left(\frac{\pi+\varphi_1}{4}+\frac{\varphi_1}{2}\right)}^{\left(\frac{\pi+\varphi_1}{4}+\frac{\varphi_1}{2}\right)} q_0(1+k_v V_e^2) L_{st} \frac{d_{ch}}{2} \left[h_{yu} - \frac{d_{ch}}{2} (1 - \cos \alpha) \right] \cos \alpha d\alpha = \\
 &= q_0(1+k_v V_e^2) L_{st} \frac{d_{ch}}{2} \int_{-\left(\frac{\pi+\varphi_1}{4}+\frac{\varphi_1}{2}\right)}^{\left(\frac{\pi+\varphi_1}{4}+\frac{\varphi_1}{2}\right)} \left[\left(h_{yu} - \frac{d_{ch}}{2} \right) \cos \alpha d\alpha + \frac{d_{ch}}{2} \cos^2 \alpha d\alpha \right] \quad (5)
 \end{aligned}$$

Integral of this expression:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q_y &= q_0(1+k_v V_e^2) L_{st} \frac{d_{ch}}{2} \times \\
 &\times \left[2 \left(h_{yu} - \frac{d_{ch}}{2} \right) \sin \left(\frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\varphi_1}{2} \right) + \frac{d_{ch}}{2} \left(\frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\varphi_1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \cos \varphi_1 \right) \right], \quad (6)
 \end{aligned}$$

Applying this result to the two upper and lower weights at the beginning of the movement, we get the following result [6, 7, 8]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q_{pa} &= q_0(1+k_v V_e^2) L_{st} \frac{d_{ch}}{2} \times \\
 &\times \left[2 \left(h_{pa} - \frac{d_{ch}}{2} \right) \sin \left(\frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\varphi_1}{2} \right) + \frac{d_{ch}}{2} \left(\frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\varphi_1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \cos \varphi_1 \right) \right] \quad (7)
 \end{aligned}$$

Taking into account expressions (6) and (7), expression (1) is written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q_{yu} &= 2q_0(1+k_v V_e^2) (b_{pe} + 2(H_{gr} - H_k) / ctg \varphi) d_{ch} \times \\
 &\times \left[\left(h_{yu} + \sqrt{H_{gr}^2 - L_{or}^2 - H_k^2} - d_{ch} \right) \sin \left(\frac{\pi}{4} + \varphi_1 \right) + \frac{d_{ch}}{2} \left(\frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\varphi_1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \cos \varphi_1 \right) \right] \quad (8)
 \end{aligned}$$

(8) substituting the values $q_0=1,1 \cdot 10^6$ N/m³, $k_v=0,01$ s²/m², $V_e=1,5$ m/s, $L_{st}=1$ m, $d_{ch}=0,004$ m, $b_{pe}=0,15$ m, $H_{gr}=0,15$ m, $H_k=0,1$ m, $h_{yu}=0,0075$ m, $L_{or}=0,025$ m, $\varphi=40^0$, $\varphi_I=30^0$ into the expression, we determine that in order for the intensifier to compress the soil at the required level, it must be subjected to a vertical load of 950 N/m.

References

1. Norchayev R., Norchayev D.R., Norchayev J.R., Rustamova N.R. Ildizmevalarni yig'ishtirish mashinalarining konstruksiyasi va nazariyasi. – Toshkent: “Fan va texnologiya” MCHJ, 2015. – 104 b.
2. G.Q. Eshmatova. Kombinatsiyalashgan mashinalar tarkibida qo'llaniladigan tandem g'altakmolaning turi va parametrlarini asoslash // Diss. ...texn. fan. nomzodi. – Gulbahor, 2023. – 154 b.
3. M.T. Mamarasulova. Shudgorlangan yerlarga izma-iz ishlov beradigan mashina g'altakmolasi turi va parametrlarini asoslash // Diss. ...texn. fan. nomzodi. – Namangan, 2021. – 151 b.

4. Jurayev B.B. (2023). Kartoshka kovlash mashinasining chiviqli intensivatori asosiy parametrlarining nazariy asoslari. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2 (14 SPECIAL), 539–542. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/4483>
5. Jurayev B.B. (2023). Kartoshka kovlagichning elaklash ishchi organlarining qiyosiy tahlili. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(12), 330–334. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/5534>
6. Jurayev B.B.(2023). Kartoshka yig'ish mashinalari elaklash ishchi organlarining tahlili. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(12), 316–319. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/5531>
7. Juraev B.B. Kinematic parameters of the intensifier with elastic rods. // “European science international conference: Analysis of Modern Science and Innovation”. Italy, 2024. –p. 67-70.
8. Urol Abdurakhmonov and Bakhodir Juraev. Dynamics of the movement of the ripping tool for surface tillage. *E3S Web Conf. Volume 264*, 2021. International Scientific Conference “Construction Mechanics, Hydraulics and Water Resources Engineering” (CONMECHYDRO - 2021)